

A Novel Bottom-Up Method Based on Advanced Similarity Weighting: Applied to Building Replacements in Zurich (2001–2019)

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1 Introduction

Two bottom-up approaches in building stock modeling (BSM) face the following limitations. The building-by-building approach enables high-resolution modeling with advanced techniques (e.g. remote sensing, computer vision) but applies primarily to existing buildings and exteriors, excluding demolished ones and interiors. The archetype approaches represent building cohorts through archetypes and extrapolate findings across the stock using up-scaling factors but relies on expert-defined categories and assumes homogeneity in material composition and intensity, leading to dataset oversimplification and loss of heterogeneity [1]. To address these issues, Fivet and team [2] introduced a novel propagation method in BSM in 2024, using a *similarity-weighting (SW)* function to estimate unknown intrinsic properties of stock buildings through a weighted average of similar samples, with weights based on stock-sample similarity. However, this method has the following limitations: (1) defining similar samples to stock buildings requires manually setting similarity thresholds, which introduces a subjective assumption; (2) defining the similarity region presents a dilemma: a larger boundary leads to broad comparisons and reduced model accuracy, while a smaller boundary defines similarity more strictly, limiting comparable samples and, especially with sparse data, leading to low validation coverage; (3) it fails to capture real-world nonlinear behavior with interval-dependent shifts, such as the varying historical trajectories of different materials. To overcome these limitations, this study proposes an *advanced-similarity-weighting (ASW)* function, offering a more robust and generalizable approach for BSM while tracing the origins of SW and evaluating its applicability and limitations.

2 Methods

2.1 Generic advanced-similarity-weighting with Softmax

The core principle of SW, originating from the *inverse-distance-weighting (IDW)* interpolation method developed in the 1960s at Harvard’s Computer Graphics and Spatial Analysis Laboratory [3], assumes that the value at an unknown geographical points is a weighted average of nearby known points, with weights inversely proportional to the distances, assigning greater weight to closer points. This method is also applied in various fields, including environmental science (e.g., air quality), geology (e.g., mineral exploration), and economics (e.g., real estate pricing). Assuming this interpolation applies to BSM, the general formula is expressed as follows:

$$M(j) = \frac{\sum_{i \in C(j)} w(i, j) M(i)}{\sum_{i \in C(j)} w(i, j)}, \quad (1)$$

where $M(i)$ and $M(j)$ represent a specific property of sample i and stock building j , such as material or emission quantity. The weight $w(i, j)$ quantifies their similarity by comparing the distance $D(i, j)$ between selected features. The term $i \in C(j)$ denotes the prerequisites for sample i relative to j to be included in the similarity comparison. The term $\sum_{i \in C(j)} w(i, j)$ serves as a normalization factor, ensuring that the total weights assigned to stock building j equals 1. Building on this, the study incorporates *Softmax* to develop the ASW method, adapting IDW for BSM, expressed in the weighting function as:

$$w(i, j) = e^{-\sigma D(i, j)}, \quad (2)$$

where $w(i, j)$ adopts an **inverse exponential function** to describe the decay of weights with increasing distance $D(i, j)$, unlike the conventional SW method proposed in Fivet et al. [2], which uses linear weighting with manually defined similarity boundaries, leading to a trade-off between model accuracy

and coverage (Figure 1). In contrast, the inverse exponential function naturally resolves this limitation by amplifying differences between input values, enhancing the weight of closely distributed samples while quickly diminishing the weights of more distant ones. This negates the need for defining a specific similarity region to mitigate distant samples' influence, as their impact naturally weakens exponentially. Thus, the improved method enhances similarity weight assignment coverage, i.e., model coverage. The decay rate of weights with increasing distance is governed by σ ; smaller values of σ lead to faster decay, and vice versa. Combining Eqs. 1 and 2, the resulting normalized weighting function follows a **Softmax** mapping, chosen for its widespread use in converting distance into similarity weights in leading language models [4]. The features F in the Euclidean distance $D(i, j) = \sqrt{\sum_k (\Delta F^k(i, j) / \tilde{F}^k)^2}$, used to quantify the separation between buildings, can be context-dependent (e.g., type, year, size), with k as feature index. The normalized term \tilde{F}^k removes units and balances the contribution of each feature to the total.

Figure 1: Diagram of weight assignments for stock building j with same sample buildings: (left) a linear weighting function in SW, derived from Fivet et al. [2]; (right) an exponential weighting function in ASW.

2.2 Specific consideration for interval dependence

The basic IDW principle in BSM assumes a smoothly distributed dataset. However, real-world phenomena often exhibit **nonlinear behavior with interval-dependent shifts**, where behaviors vary across conditions or ranges and may shift abruptly at critical points. For instance, material elasticity varies with stress levels, and biological growth rates shift with age. In buildings, material usage does not always follow a continuous trend, with discontinuities arising at critical points, such as structural material per unit area surging beyond certain heights or materials phasing in and out due to technological evolution. Such variations challenge IDW's smooth distribution assumption, necessitating an alternative. A **piecewise function** naturally captures behavioral differences in feature F^k across distinct intervals. To align similarity estimation with the piecewise nature in ASW, a **dynamic similarity boundary** is introduced to constrain comparisons within the same behavioral regime while adapting to threshold shifts across evolving piecewise regimes. To incorporate interval dependence into the generic ASW formulation, distance formula $D(i, j)$ replaces the fixed normalized term \tilde{F}^k with an inequality involving **radius scaling function (RSF)** $F_p^k(j)$, which captures the dynamic similarity boundary, namely,

$$|\Delta F^k(i, j) / F_p^k(j)| \leq 1. \quad (3)$$

3 Application and Validation

ASW is applied to building replacements in Zurich City from 2001 to 2019 to estimate the inflow and outflow of structural materials and embodied greenhouse gas emissions (EGHGEs). The stock dataset includes 3,359 demolished and 2,756 newly constructed buildings. The sample dataset, derived from Fivet et al. [5], consists of 48 Swiss buildings with detailed superstructural data, excluding foundations, stairs, and balconies. Construction materials—reinforced concrete, metals, timber, and masonry—are evaluated in terms of volume, mass, and EGHGE (phases A1–A3 per EN-15978). Similarity weights between stock and sample buildings are computed based on functionality, built year, footprint, and height. Compared to the SW application in Fivet et al. [2], this study enhances material-specific estimation in ASW by introducing distinct RSF for three materials to capture historical evolution and adoption rates.

Parameter selection. The parameter σ in weighting function is empirically set to 0.8, achieving a local minimum mean error rate and resulting in a rapid decay rate in the weighting. The normalization factors \tilde{F} for year, footprint, and height are determined based on their standard deviations across datasets.

Cross validation. Leave-one-out cross-validation evaluates method effectiveness by comparing mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and model coverage (Table 1). ASW achieves full coverage, while SW reaches 87.5%. ASW also provides more accurate estimates, with overall accuracy between 75–80%. Compared with Support Vector Machine (SVM), a classic machine learning technique effective for training on small to medium datasets. Results show ASW matches or outperforms SVM. As estimation granularity increases for breakdown materials, both methods see rising error rates, with ASW generally performing better, while a higher presence of zero values in the sample set correlates with increased error rates.

Correlation between measures. The high cosine similarity and Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) between the estimated measures confirm strong correlations, further validating ASW. Moreover, the PCC values are higher for new construction, indicating better model performance for these buildings.

Table 1: Comparison of model effectiveness among SW, Softmax-SW, and SVM methods.

Estimated measures	Number of 0 value in sample library	SW		ASW(Softmax)			SVM (auto optimize)	
		Coverage \uparrow	MAPE \downarrow	Coverage \uparrow	MAPE	\downarrow	Coverage \uparrow	MAPE \downarrow
EGHGE	0	87.5%	26.74%	100%	20.58 %		100%	20.08%
Volume	0	87.5%	31.21%	100%	25.75 %		100%	37.26%
Mass	0	87.5%	33.98%	100%	26.71 %		100%	26.42%
concrete mass	3	—	—	100%	44.96% (+RSF _c)		100%	89.19%
metal mass	36	—	—	100%	453.71% (+RSF _m)		100%	399.32%
timber mass	31	—	—	100%	46.64% (+RSF _{ts})		100%	132.94%
masonry mass	26	—	—	100%	63.90% (+RSF _{ts})		100%	41.76%

4 Results

The results obtained using the ASW method reveal that, while new constructions had 2.44 times the total volume of demolished buildings, their structural volume, mass, and EGHGEs (A1–A3) were 2.26, 2.53, and 2.24 times higher, respectively. Slabs and walls dominated EGHGEs, contributing 85% in demolished and up to 92% in new buildings. Concrete remained the primary structural material, comprising 85% of demolished and 99% of new structural mass. Multi-residential and office buildings accounted for 75.7% and 15.2% of new structural concrete use. Structural EGHGEs per unit (in kgCO₂eq/m²) for residential buildings (211 for demolished, 218 for new) were slightly above the 25th percentile structural GWP (around 200, A1–A3) in the deQo database, likely due to excluding foundations and staircases.

5 Discussion

ASW provides a generalizable bottom-up method for BSM, with parametric flexibility allowing extension to other cities’ databases. The method scales well, as its comparison features can be expanded into high-dimensional models, and its accuracy improves with sample size. ASW performs effectively with limited samples, even outperforming machine learning in such cases, making it ideal for BSM, where data scarcity results from manual collection. IDW-based methods assume smooth data variation, making them well-suited for applications where industry trends are stable, such as structural and envelope assemblies. In contrast, assemblies like finishes, influenced by user preferences, exhibit greater variability, introducing higher uncertainty in ASW assignment. The ASW approach supports environmental impact assessments aligned with circular economy principles, contributing to sustainable urban resource management.

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